

Socialization of Education in the Southeast Region Contributes to Improving the Quality of Education and Training in the Current Period

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Article History:

Received: 15.09.2025 Revised: 06.10.2025 Accepted: 07.10.2025 Published: 08.10.2025

Abstract

Since the mid-1990s, in Vietnam, the participation of non-state components in the provision of some types of public services has been institutionalized. According to Resolution No. 90/CP of the Government dated August 21, 1997 on the direction and policy of socialization of educational, medical and cultural activities: "Socialization of educational, medical and cultural activities is to mobilize and organize the broad participation of the people and the whole society in the development of those causes in order to gradually improve the level of enjoyment of education, medical, cultural and physical and spiritual development of the people...". After the Resolution was issued, it promoted the socialization of education to mobilize the participation of the whole society in the development of the educational cause, build a healthy educational environment, encourage everyone and every organization to contribute to the development of education and enjoy the results of education.

Keywords: *Socialization, socialization of education, quality, human resources.*

Suggested citation: Trong, N.P. (2025). Socialization of Education in the Southeast Region Contributes to Improving the Quality of Education and Training in the Current Period. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 182-190. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).19](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).19)

Introduction

The Southeast Region includes Ho Chi Minh City and 05 provinces: Tay Ninh, Binh Phuoc, Binh Duong, Dong Nai, Ba Ria - Vung Tau, with an area of 23,551.5 km², the second smallest region in the country (accounting for 7.1% of the country's area); the population in 2022 is 18.8 million people (accounting for 18.9% of the country's population). The Southeast Region has a particularly important position and role in the country's socio-economic development; converging most of the outstanding conditions and advantages to develop industry and services, taking the lead in industrialization and modernization; especially developing high-tech industry, semiconductor industry, electronics,

information technology, oil and gas industry and petrochemical products; developing high-end services, financial services, banking, tourism, telecommunications; researching, applying and deploying science and technology; training highly qualified human resources; developing specialized medical services.

Implementing Resolution No. 90/CP of the Government; Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013 of the Eighth Conference (XI Central Executive Committee) on "Fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training, meeting the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the conditions of a socialist-oriented market economy and international integration";

Education Development Strategy 2011 - 2020, the work of socializing education in the Southeast region has achieved initial results, but there are still many difficulties and shortcomings. Investment in education from the state budget is increasing but has not met the people's learning needs, while social resources for general education from the policy of socialized education are still very limited. This article aims to clarify the advantages, difficulties and the process of implementing socialized education in the Southeast region, thereby drawing lessons and proposing some solutions to improve the quality of socialized education in the provinces and cities to meet the needs of training human resources to serve the socio-economic development in the Southeast region.

Research Content and Results

Overview of Research Situation on Socialization

Socialization of education has also received much attention from researchers: Hoang Duc Minh (2009), "Some models of high schools implementing the policy of socialization of education in Quang Ninh province", *Journal of Education*, No. 214, pp. 9-10. The article approaches the issue of socialization of general education in Quang Ninh province through models of public and non-public high schools and vocational schools. From these school models, significant resources have been attracted for education, contributing to the implementation of the policy of socialization of education that Quang Ninh province has identified (Hoang Duc Minh, 2009, No. 214).

Explaining the terminology and theoretical basis, many articles delve into the analysis and theoretical research of socialization of education in general. Author Nguyen Huu Khien (2014) has an article: "Socialization of education: benefits and barriers" published in the *Journal of Social Sciences of Vietnam*. The article shows the development process of awareness of theoretical issues of socialization of education, especially the conceptual connotation. Up to now, although the use of the term socialization in Vietnam has been popular and unified, these articles help later researchers understand the history of the issue more deeply, and at the same

time clearly see the dialectical nature of the awareness process (Nguyen Huu Khien, 2014).

Author Luong Thi Viet Ha (2016) has an article: "Some theoretical issues on the management of socialization of education participation activities of Vietnamese high schools" published in the *Journal of Education*, No. 312 (term 2 - 6/2013). The article points out: The nature of socialization of education is the mobilization of all social forces together with the State to participate in the cause of education in general and high school education in particular. For effective socialization of education, the management of educational participation activities of social forces or good management of the relationship "School - Family - Society" is very important. At the same time, the author also introduces some concepts; approaches to mobilizing and managing socialization activities of high schools; relationships and guiding principles to mobilize social forces to participate in managing socialization activities of high schools; criteria and processes for managing socialization activities of high schools; high school councils (Luong Thi Viet Ha, 2016).

Author Pham Thi Thu Huong (2017) with the book: "Socialization of education in Vietnam today: some theoretical and practical issues", National Political Publishing House - Truth. The content of the book focuses on clarifying some theoretical issues on socialization of education such as: the concept of socialization of education, content Socialization of Education and the Inevitability of Implementing Socialization of Education in Vietnam. At the same time, the book also analyzes the current situation and discusses the issues raised in the process of implementing Socialization of Education in Vietnam in recent times. From there, it determines the direction and proposes a number of solutions to effectively implement Socialization of Education in Vietnam in the current period (Pham Thi Thu Huong, 2017).

Author Nguyen Thi Kim Lien with the research: "The current situation of socialization of education and training in Binh Duong province in recent times" in the *Journal of Political Science*, 2019, stated that: Socialization of Education is a major policy of the Party and the

State, an important task of the whole society. In essence, this is the mobilization of economic and intellectual contributions from the whole society to increase resources for education and training activities, creating conditions for people to have the opportunity to enjoy the achievements in the field of education. The Binh Duong provincial government has thoroughly grasped the Party's policies and the State's policies, and has many measures implementation. With appropriate measures, Binh Duong province has attracted social resources for education and training development and achieved important results (Nguyen Thi Kim Lien, 2019).

The article by author Manh Hung "Approving the Project on Building a Learning Society for the 2021-2030 period" published in the Communist Party Electronic Magazine said: On July 30, 2021, the Prime Minister issued Decision 1373/QD-TTg approving the Project "Building a Learning Society for the 2021-2030 period". According to the Project, the Socialization of education means that all people have equal opportunities to access an open, diverse, flexible, interconnected, and modern education system with many models, methods, and levels of training, contributing to promoting human resource development (Manh Hung, 2021).

Socialization of education is a broad topic, attracting the research attention of many scientists, many scientific fields and many political and social organizations abroad. The number of research works referring to the current state of socialization of education is very rich and massive, presented from many different perspectives. Among these works, we can mention some of the following typical works:

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), whose purpose is to find out policies for economic development and people's welfare, has published a separate journal called Higher Education Management and Policy. The journal was first published in 1977 under the name of the International Journal of Institutional Management in Higher Education and was renamed the Journal of Higher Education Management in the period 1989-2001. The journal is published three times a year in English. In order to implement the goals

within the framework of the OECD Higher Education Program, most of the research articles in the journal focus on the practice and solutions for innovation in higher education in countries. Some typical articles in the anthology 13 part 1 in 2001 can be mentioned: Futao Huang (Hiroshima University, Japan): "Diversifying Sources of Funding in Chinese Higher Education" examines the reform and changes in financial policies for public higher education after 1992 (Futao Huang, 2001). Author Ian Dodson (Monash University, Australia): "Go Forth and Diversify! The Rise and Fall of Government Contributions to Australian Higher Education" examines the changes in the proportion of budget expenditure on higher education from the establishment of the first universities until 1998. This proportion has changed from 90% to less than 52% in just 25 years (Ian Dodson, 2001).

Author Cotton Kathleen in the book: "Relationships in schools are the greatest concerns" wrote about the participation of parents in the education society, including different forms such as: Parents can support their children's learning by participating in subjects and meeting learning obligations. They can participate more in helping their children, monitoring homework, actively tutoring their children at home to improve their learning, encouraging, creating conditions of time, suitable study space as well as meeting the wishes of their children. They can have an active role in the administration and decision-making necessary for planning and developing education for children. The author also gave evidence that the participation of parents in their children's learning activities has helped them achieve higher academic achievements (Cotton, K., 2000).

Cynthia V.Crites's thesis: "Parent and community involvement: a case study". The research thesis is based on a case analysis, describing ways to increase the participation of parents and the community in the process of socialization of education. The study shows that to increase the participation of parents and the community, schools must involve them in the decision-making process and planning of school activities. In addition, schools need to provide

professional training for teachers so that they can solve problems related to parents. The author also gives some influences and barriers when parents want to participate in the school, from which there are solutions to solve the barriers to get parents more involved in school work (Cynthia V.Crites, 2008). Marie DeLuci's thesis, titled "A Case Study of Social Participation in Primary Schools in Three Schools in Ethiopia" has pointed out the importance of community participation in school development. At the same time, the author has demonstrated that in order to mobilize the participation of parents and the community, there needs to be an organization or a committee representing the community or parents to improve the school, especially the need for coordinated efforts between the State - parents and non-governmental organizations in caring for the school as well as their children (Marie DeLucia Ternieden, 2009).

The Party and State's Viewpoints on Socialization of Education

Socialization of educational activities is a major policy of the Party and the State, which has initially achieved certain results in mobilizing social resources to meet the increasing needs of all classes of people. Implementing the national renovation, the economy has initially developed, but many social issues, including education, have raised many urgent issues that need to be resolved. In that situation, the Party and the State have had many major policies and strategies to develop the education cause, one of which is to socialize educational activities. Previously, although the concept of socialization was not used, the Strategy for socio-economic stability and development until 2000, approved at the 7th Party Congress, initiated the idea of exploiting all potentials of the whole society to participate in developing education and training. Resolution No. 04-NQ/HNTW (Session VII) dated January 14, 1993 officially proposed the policy of "diversifying training forms". Based on the Party's viewpoint, state agencies have issued policies and guidelines to promote socialization of educational activities. Resolution No. 90/CP dated August 21, 1997 of the Government on the direction and policy of socialization of educational, health and cultural activities clearly

stated the contents of socialization.

Accordingly, socialization of educational activities is to mobilize and organize the broad participation of the people and the whole society in the development of those causes in order to gradually improve the level of educational enjoyment and the physical and spiritual development of the people. Socialization is building a community of responsibility among all classes of people for creating and improving a healthy and favorable economic and social environment for educational activities in each locality. This is a community of responsibility among the Party Committee, People's Council, People's Committee, mass organizations, economic organizations, businesses located in the locality and each individual.

The policy of socialization of education continues to be clarified in the Resolutions of the VIII and IX Congresses of the Party: Socialization of education is to mobilize the whole society to do education, to encourage all classes of people to contribute to building national education under the management of the State; social policies are carried out in the spirit of socialization, promoting the responsibility of authorities at all levels, mobilizing resources among the people and the participation of people's organizations and social organizations.

The Resolution of the 2nd Conference of the Party Central Committee (VIII term) on the strategic orientation for education and training development in the period of industrialization and modernization and the tasks until 2000 clearly stated, "Institutionalizing the policy of socializing education as stated in the Resolution of the 8th Congress". Implementing the stated policy of socializing education, the Government issued Resolution No. 90/CP dated August 21, 1997 on the direction and policy of socializing education, health, and cultural activities. After the above Resolution of the 2nd Central Committee of the 8th term, the Law on Education was issued in 1998, for the first time recognizing the multi-ownership regime for educational institutions, including public, semi-public, private and private. The Resolution of the 10th National Party Congress (2006) affirmed that the State will continue to increase resources and focus investment on national

target programs on education, while promoting the intelligence and material resources of the people and the whole society to join the State in solving social issues and taking care of the development of public service sectors.

Based on the assessment of the results of implementing the socialization of education, health, culture and sports after 7 years of implementing Resolution No. 90/CP, the Government Resolution No. 05/NQ-CP dated April 18, 2005 on promoting the socialization of education, health, culture and sports activities has proposed viewpoints and orientations for the development of socialization in the fields of education, health, culture, sports as well as major solutions and policy mechanisms. The main orientations to promote socialization are identified as: 1) The State innovates policy mechanisms and investment structure methods; 2) Converts public institutions operating under a heavily subsidized administrative career mechanism to an autonomous mechanism; 3) Strongly develops non-public institutions with two types: private and public; 4) Strengthens inspection and examination activities.

On June 14, 2005, the National Assembly passed the Law on Education, identifying education development as the top national policy to improve people's knowledge, train human resources, and foster talents; education development must be linked to the needs of economic and social development; "Developing education and building a learning society is the cause of the State and the entire people. The State plays a leading role in developing the education cause; diversifying school types and forms of education; encouraging, mobilizing and creating conditions for organizations and individuals to participate in developing the education cause" (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2005).

In 2012, the Government issued Resolution No. 40/NQ-CP on Socialization of Education. In recent years, the policy of Socialization of Education has been further directed by the Central Committee in Resolution No. 29/NQ-TU dated November 4, 2013 on fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training. The Resolution determined:

"Proactively promote the positive aspects, limit the negative aspects of the market mechanism, ensure the socialist orientation in the development of education and training. Harmoniously develop and support between public and non-public education, between regions and areas. Prioritize investment in education and training development for particularly difficult areas, ethnic minority areas, border areas, islands, remote areas and policy subjects. Implement democratization and socialization of education and training" (Central Committee, 2013). On June 14, 2019, at the 7th Session, the 14th National Assembly passed the 2019 Law on Education. With the goal of institutionalizing the Party's policies and guidelines and the State's laws on education and training innovation, creating a legal corridor for the construction of a comprehensively developed Vietnamese education system; The Law defines: "Diversify types of educational institutions and forms of education; encourage, mobilize and create conditions for organizations and individuals to participate in developing the education career; encourage the development of non-public and private educational institutions to meet social needs for education" (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2019). It can be said that the above political and legal bases are important bases for the socialization of education to be recognized and developed and become an indispensable part of the general picture of Vietnam's educational development in recent years.

Policies of the Party Committee and Local Authorities of the Provinces and Cities in the Southeast Region on the Socialization of Education

Mobilizing resources and facilities for education

Over the past 5 years of implementation (2011 - 2015), the international and domestic situation has faced many difficulties and severe challenges, but the Party Committee, government, and people of all walks of life in the Southeast region have continued to promote the tradition of solidarity, dynamism, and creatively applied the Central's policies and guidelines in accordance with local realities, effectively

exploited potentials, advantages, and resources, created social consensus, and strived to achieve important and quite comprehensive achievements. Regarding the implementation of the policy of socializing education, the Party Committees and governments of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region have thoroughly grasped the Central Resolution on fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training, which has been focused on implementation in conjunction with the implementation of local human resource development planning and programs. Focus on investing in facilities, equipment and strengthening the teaching staff, basically meeting the needs of teaching and learning.

Entering the period of 2015 - 2018, the results achieved in the previous period, as well as the socio-economic achievements, solidarity, unity, initiative and creativity in leadership and management of Party committees and authorities at all levels are important driving forces for the Party Committees and authorities of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region and all classes of people to successfully implement the goals and tasks of socio-economic development, including education and training. Regarding the policy of socializing education, the Party Committees and authorities of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region determined: Developing education and training, meeting the needs of improving people's knowledge, training human resources; implementing well Resolution 29-NQ/TW on fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training, meeting the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the conditions of a socialist-oriented market economy and international integration; Pay attention to investing in building new schools in line with national standards, increasing the rate of schools meeting national standards to 70-75%; encourage and promote socialization to increase investment sources, contributing to ensuring the increasing demand for learning, especially in industrial and urban areas; focus on improving the quality of education at all levels.

Developing the team of managers and teachers

After 5 years of implementation (2006-2010), the provinces and cities in the Southeast region have achieved important achievements, developed quite comprehensively, had many bright spots, had many aspects of strong development and left many marks. In particular, the education and training sector has many aspects of progress, educational and training facilities have been invested in the direction of "solidification, standardization, modernization, socialization". The teaching staff is guaranteed in quantity, structure and meets standards in qualifications. The quality of education has been improved, the rate of high school graduates and university and college graduates has increased. Education and training has had positive changes in the implementation of the task of training human resources, improving people's knowledge, and nurturing talents to serve the socio-economic development of the region. In particular, the education career has changed positively in the direction of improving the quality of comprehensive education along with key education, contributing to training human resources, improving people's knowledge, and nurturing talents to serve the socio-economic development of the locality. The network of schools, scale, and quality of education and training continue to develop in all fields of study and levels of education. 100% of communes, wards, and towns have maintained the results of eliminating illiteracy and universalizing primary and secondary education; 20.5% of schools have met national standards. 99.63% of children of the age group are mobilized to attend primary school. The work of socialization of education has been promoted to strengthen the material facilities and equipment for schools and to realize the goal of building a learning society. However, the number of teachers and managers is still insufficient, the quality is uneven; the material facilities serving education and training are still lacking.

Expanding the scale of training and diversifying the types of schools

Entering the period 2011 - 2015, is a very important period for the socio-economic

development of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region towards industrialization and modernization. Therefore, the Party Committees and authorities of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region have determined the goals and directions for innovation and improvement of the quality and effectiveness of education and training in this period: Continuing to comprehensively and strongly innovate and develop education and training to meet the requirements of improving people's knowledge, developing high-quality human resources, building new, comprehensively developed people with the capacity to master their lives, work and contribute to society; building a learning society on the basis of the movement to encourage learning, encourage talents and the tradition of studiousness of the Vietnamese people. Continue to improve the development planning towards diversifying the system of education types, balancing appropriately between public and private schools; synchronously developing the general education system, continuing education, and vocational training. Develop an open education model with flexible forms of learning and practice, meeting the people's regular learning needs. Promote socialization closely linked with standardization and modernization; attract all domestic and foreign resources to develop schools, especially vocational schools; promote learning and talent promotion along with enhancing the role of State management in education and training.

To achieve the above goals and directions, the Party Committees and authorities of the provinces and cities in the Southeast region have identified a number of key solutions, in which promoting socialization and mobilizing the whole society to take care of developing education and training are identified as important solutions. Accordingly, develop the scale and improve the quality of comprehensive education, especially focusing on education on revolutionary traditions, ideals, ethics, lifestyle, creativity, practical skills, industrial style, and sense of social responsibility. Implement well the work of career guidance and career orientation for students; physical education, improve school health and school hygiene. Implement the project of universalizing preschool education for

5-year-old children. Strengthen training and fostering of teachers to achieve above-standard qualifications, further improve management capacity and pedagogical capacity. Innovate the mechanism of education and training management. Reasonable implementation of the autonomy mechanism for educational and training institutions associated with innovation of financial mechanisms; conduct quality assessment of education and training at all levels and announce and publicize the results of quality assessment of education and training; organize the ranking of educational and training institutions. Building a healthy educational environment, closely combining school with family and society.

Some Solutions to Improve the Quality of Socialized Education in the Southeast Region Today

Firstly, promoting the role of the political system in the Southeast in implementing the socialization of general education.

Entering the country's renewal process, the Party has issued policies and resolutions on building a learning society, innovating education and training, moving towards socialized education; typically, the Resolution of the 10th National Congress of the Party stated "Gradually shifting the current education model to an open education model, a learning society model". This is a new development in educational thinking according to Resolution 02-NQ/HNTW of the 8th term dated December 24, 1996. Resolution 29-NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013 of the Central Executive Committee continues to implement Resolution 02-NQ/HNTW of the 8th term "Considering education and training as the top national policy" and "Fundamental and comprehensive innovation of education and training". In parallel with the resolution on "Fundamental and comprehensive innovation in education and training", on April 13, 2007, the Politburo issued Directive 11-CT/TW on "Strengthening the Party's leadership in promoting learning, talent, and building a learning society" and after 10 years of implementing Directive 11-CT/TW, on May 10, 2019, the Secretariat issued Conclusion 49-KL/TW on continuing to implement Directive

11-CT/TW of the Politburo in the new period. In this Conclusion 49-KL/TW, the Secretariat assigned more specific responsibilities to Party organizations and Party members in the learning society and must be exemplary in implementing learning models, assigning the Vietnam Association for Promoting Education to be the core in coordinating and implementing the movement to promote learning, talent, and building a learning society in localities and units.

Second, Promoting the role of organizations, forces and people in the socialization of general education.

Socialization of education is a major policy of the Party and the State, but the awareness of the importance and significance of this policy has not been truly unified in management levels from the central to local levels and among people, in many localities and educational institutions, leading to difficulties in implementation. This leads to a slow socialization speed, not commensurate with the potential and not being able to mobilize all social resources to develop education and training. In addition, although non-public general education institutions have increased rapidly in number, in general, their scale is still small, their facilities are limited, their development is uneven, and they are mainly concentrated in the inner city, inner town, and densely populated areas. Large and medium-sized urban areas, areas with highly developed socio-economic conditions; Social resources attracted to the non-public education sector are still low, the level of resource mobilization between regions, areas and localities is still different. The level of socialization is still low in suburban and remote areas, difficult areas, services are still lacking compared to demand, the quality of in-depth expertise has not been achieved in the public sector; the staff and teachers are still lacking and weak, the quality and efficiency of operations are not high. People's psychology is still waiting for the care of the state, the management of foreign-invested schools, the management of educational service business organizations is still inadequate due to the lack of a legal document system.

Thirdly, focus on attracting social resources in the socialization of general education

Regarding investment in education, although this is a priority field and education is identified as the top national policy, the state budget for education investment is limited. Most localities in the Southeast have difficulties in funding for education investment, especially those that have not yet balanced their budgets. In that context, the funding from socialized education has not yet met the educational and training needs of all classes of people. The implementation of policies to encourage socialization in the field of education and training still faces many difficulties and obstacles, so it has not really attracted investors. Practice in the Southeast shows that administrative procedures, preferential policies on exemption and reduction of land use fees and land rent; conditions for accessing land funds to build non-public educational institutions; policies on reclamation and site clearance for the construction of educational facilities; policies on tax exemption and reduction, credit incentives, and investment in the form of public-private partnerships... have not yet ensured ease of implementation. In addition, there is a lack of specific regulations on the rights and responsibilities of individuals and organizations when investing in the development of non-public educational institutions. This reduces the attractiveness and appeal of investors to education, leading to the attraction of social resources for general education in the Southeast region in recent times with many limitations and shortcomings. It is urgent to continue to improve incentive policies and create favorable conditions for domestic and foreign investors to invest in education and training development at all levels and training levels.

Conclusion

Socialization of education to attract domestic and foreign investment has become a major, long-term and consistent policy, deeply understood and widely implemented to all levels, sectors, political organizations, socio-political organizations and all classes of people. Socialization has brought positive effects to the education cause in the Southeast in recent times,

but this work has given rise to many shortcomings that need to be resolved, especially the limited investment funding and many difficulties. Party committees and authorities of provinces and cities in the Southeast region are in great need of mechanisms and policies to strengthen socialization, mobilize maximum investment resources for education and training development.

References

Bui, H., Nguyen Van Giao, Nguyen Huu Quynh, & Vu Van Tao. (2001). *Dictionary of Education*. Hanoi: Encyclopedia.

Bui, T. (2020). Promoting the propaganda of socialization of education in Hanoi. *Communist Magazine*, (12), 32–35.

Bui, T. H. (2004, No. 12). Developing human resource education — implementing the policy of socialization of education. *Finance Magazine*, 16–18.

Bui, T. H. (2005). Socialization of education: need for appropriate tuition regime. *Finance Magazine*, (5), 19–21.

Ministry of Education and Training. (2020). *Circular No. 28/2020/TT-BGDĐT dated September 4, 2020 of the Ministry of Education and Training on promulgating the charter of primary schools*. Hanoi.

Ministry of Education and Training. (2020). *Circular No. 32/2020/TT-BGDĐT dated September 15, 2020 of the Ministry of Education and Training on promulgating the charter of junior high schools, high schools and multi-level general schools*. Hanoi.

Politburo. (2022). *Resolution No. 24 - NQ/TW dated October 7, 2022 of the Politburo on socio-economic development and ensuring national defense and security in the Southeast region until 2030, with a vision to 2045*. Hanoi.